

Thermal studies on some transition metal complexes with *N,N'*-triethylenediaminebis(3-carboxypropenamide)

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Thermogravimetric studies of manganese(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of *N,N'*-triethylenediaminebis(3-carboxypropenamide) [TEBCPH₂] have been carried out which give valuable information about the temperature of inception, of maximum rate and of complete decomposition. The thermal decomposition of the complexes of manganese(II) and cobalt(II) occurs in three stages whereas that of nickel(II) and copper(II) in two stages. These stages of decomposition are attributed to the removal of the ligand from the complex. The residue is due to the presence of the metal oxide. In addition to this, the kinetic parameters such as energy of activation (*E*), pre-exponential factor (*A*) and the entropy of activation (ΔS) have been determined by Coats-Redfern equation. The negative ΔS values of the first stage of decomposition of nickel(II) complex and that of the manganese(II) complex show that the activated complexes are more ordered than the reactants. The ΔS values for all other stages of decomposition are positive which indicate that the activated complexes are less ordered in structure compared to the reactants.

In continuation of our earlier studies¹, in the present communication we report the non-isothermal thermogravimetric² studies of the manganese(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of TEBCPH₂. The structure of the ligand is,

Results and discussion

The TG-DTG curve of the manganese(II) complex with TEBCPH₂ is shown in Fig. 1. Similar TG-DTG curves are obtained for the other complexes. For the complex [Ni(TEBCP)], the TG plateau upto 383 K shows its stability and the complex starts decomposition after this temperature. There are two decomposition stages with 40 and 36.5 percent mass loss at 411.1 K and 580.2 K. The first stage of decomposition is attributed to the removal of two fragments of -CO-CH=CH-CO of the ligand retaining the basic coordination geometry. This would produce a theoretical mass loss of 41% which is closer to the experimental value. For the second stage loss of the fragment -NH-(CH₂)₂-NH-(CH₂)₂-NH-(CH₂)₂-NH takes place.

Fig. 1. TG/DTG curve of [Mn(TEBCP)].

The Cu^{II} complex of TEBCPH₂ is found to be stable upto 378 K as shown by the TG plateau upto this temperature. The thermal decomposition of the complex occurs in two stages. The first stage of decomposition starts from 378 K and ends at 512 K. The peak temperature at this stage is 416.2 K. The mass loss due to loss of CO₂ is 8.8%. The second stage of decomposition is from 513 K to 633 K with 54.1% mass loss due to loss of the ligand. A brownish black residue of mixed copper oxide (28%) is obtained.

For the cobalt(II) complex, the first stage of decomposition is from 383 K to 473 K (31% mass loss); the second

stage is from 473 K to 593 K (14% mass loss) sharp peak is observed in the DTG curve at 410 K. The third stage is from 593 K to 723 K (mass loss 31.31%). These are due to loss of various parts of the complex. A dark brown residue of 24% is attributed to the mixed oxides of cobalt.

The thermal decomposition of the complex, [Mn(TEBCP)] also occurs in three stages. These are 378–533 K (40% loss), 533–613 K (10% loss) and 613–693 K (25.6% loss) and a residue (24.4%) is finally obtained.

Table 1. Phenomenological data of decomposition of the complexes

Complex	Stage of decomposition	T_i (K)	T_f (K)	T_s (K)	Mass loss%
[Mn(TEBCP)]	(I)	378	533	405.6	40
	(II)	533	613	566.5	10
	(III)	613	693	649.4	25.6
[Co(TEBCP)]	(I)	380	473	410	31
	(II)	473	593	551.5	14
	(III)	593	723	682.7	31
[Ni(TEBCP)]	(I)	383	493	411	40
	(II)	493	633	580.2	36.5
[Cu ₂ (TEBCP)(OH) ₂]	(I)	378	513	416.2	8.8
	(II)	513	633	524.8	54.1

The phenomenological data for the decomposition stages of the complexes are given in Table 1. The kinetic parameters were evaluated by the Coats-Redfern equation³,

$$\log \frac{g(\alpha)}{T^2} = \log \left[\frac{AR}{\phi E} (1 - 2RT/E) \right] - \frac{E}{2.303 RT}$$

Since $\frac{2RT}{E} \ll 1$, it may be neglected. So the plot of $\log g(\alpha)/T^2$ versus $1/T$ should give a straight-line with slope $-E/2.303R$. From this, E i.e. the energy of activation can be calculated. The pre-exponential factor, A , is calculated from the intercept, $\log AR/\phi E$. The entropy of activation, ΔS was calculated with the aid of the relation,

$$A = \frac{kT_s}{h} e^{\Delta S/R}, \text{ where } k = \text{Boltzmann constant, } h =$$

Planck's constant, ΔS = entropy of activation, T_s = DTG peak temperature or summit temperature and R is the gas constant. This can be rearranged to,

$$\log A = \log \frac{kT_s}{h} + \frac{\Delta S}{R}$$

The α values are obtained from the TG curves. The values of kinetic parameters obtained from the linear graphs for

$g(\alpha)/T^2$ versus $1/T$ for the various stages of decomposition of the manganese(II) and other complexes are given in Table 2.

Experimental

Table 2. Kinetic parameters for the thermal decomposition of the nickel(II), copper(II), cadmium(II) and manganese(II) complexes with TEBCPH₂

Complex	E (kJ mol ⁻¹)	A (s ⁻¹)	ΔS (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
[NiL] stage I	111.3	1.1×10^{13}	-11.1
[NiL] stage II	254.1	1.7×10^{22}	163.5
[Cu ₂ L(OH) ₂] stage I	145.5	3.9×10^{18}	96.7
[Cu ₂ L(OH) ₂] stage II	253.3	2.8×10^{24}	209.9
[CoL] stage I	154.7	2.9×10^{19}	113.4
[CoL] stage II	143.4	6.3×10^{13}	2.4
[CoL] stage III	246.9	6.6×10^{17}	76.3
[MnL] stage I	75.7	1.3×10^9	-86.1
[MnL] stage II	202.1	1.6×10^{18}	86.7
[MnL] stage III	188.8	2.3×10^{14}	11.8

L = TEBCP²⁻.

The chemicals used were of A.R. grade or of pure quality. The solvents were double-distilled. The ligand TEBCPH₂ was prepared by literature method¹. The complexes were prepared by refluxing equal volumes of solution of the respective metal salt and the ligand, TEBCPH₂ in methanol solvent in the molar ratio 1 : 1. The resulting solution was concentrated to half of its volume and allowed to cool. The solid complexes formed were filtered, washed with water and acetone and finally dried over anhydrous calcium chloride.

The TG and DTG curves of the complexes were recorded on a thermal analyser model STA 409C with a heating rate of 25°/10 min in static air from ambient to ~1000°C. The mass percentage vs temperature curves obtained were re-drawn in appropriate scales. Independent pyrolysis experiment in air was also carried out for each of the complexes studied and loss of mass determined in each case was compared with that obtained from TG. In addition to this, the kinetic parameters were determined by Coats-Redfern method using a computer programme.

References

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